

Optimisation of the Higher-Order Finite-Volume Unstructured Code Enhancement for Compressible Turbulent Flows

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Abstract

The Higher-Order finite-Volume unstructured code Enhancement (HOVE2) is an open-source software in the field of computational-fluid-dynamics (CFD). This code enables to do the simulation of compressible turbulent flows. In this White Paper, we report on optimisations of the HOVE2 code implemented in the course of the PRACE Preparatory Access Type C project “HOVE2” in the time frame of December 2018 to June 2019. A focus of optimisation was an implementation of the ParMETIS support and MPI-IO. Through the optimisation of the MPI collective communications significant speedups have been achieved. In particular, the acceleration of the write time of the MPI-IO compared to the normal I/O on 70 compute nodes amounted to 180 times.

Keywords: HOVE2, CFD, Fortran, ParMETIS, type incompatibility, MPI-IO

Introduction

Unstructured meshes are nowadays enjoying success in various field of science and engineering for representing complicated geometries. For high-fidelity unsteady turbulent simulations, where more spatial and temporal resolution is required, high-order numerical methods are ideal for harnessing the ever-increasing computing power available. These methods have been successfully used in the past in a series of applications, including subsonic, supersonic, hypersonic flows, atmospheric modelling etc. [1]-[16]. The Higher-Order finite-Volume unstructured code Enhancement for compressible turbulent flows (HOVE2) project concerns the further enabling work for the UCNS3D code.

Previous development of the UCNS3D CFD solver in the HOVE2 code has been done in the PRACE type C project associated with optimisation of the implementation of very high-order numerical schemes for unstructured meshes resulted in a 8.5 speedup. This was achieved by restructuring some of the computational intensive algorithms, employing linear algebra libraries and combining the state-of-the-art parallel frameworks of MPI and OpenMP. These developments have been applied to Large Eddy Simulations (LES) of canonical flows and RANS simulations of full aircraft geometries during take-off and landing [5].

The current PRACE type C project aims to enable extremely large scale simulations by focusing on the mesh partitioning algorithms and on the I/O of the UCNS3D CFD code in order to perform ILES simulations on unstructured meshes in the scale of billion cells with very high-order finite volume methods. This enables us to improve our understanding of the aerodynamic performance of complicated geometries with the goal to enhance their efficiency.

In this paper we provide an overview of the optimisation of the HOVE2 code. In Section 1 we would describe the HOVE2 code, Section 2 is devoted to the software and hardware used for instrumentation. In Section 3 the main performance bottlenecks are listed. Results of the optimisation are given in Section 4. Further optimisation recommendations are presented in Section 5. In the last Section, we give a conclusion of the work.

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1. UCNS3D Code

The UCNS3D code [5] is a CFD code using the finite-volume framework for compressible flows. The code uses hybrid unstructured meshes, very high-order numerical methods (WENO, MUSCL), and various turbulence modelling techniques (RANS, DDES, ILES). The UCNS3D solver is written in the FORTRAN 2003 programming language and is making use of object oriented programming techniques including abstract data types. It employs the Message Passing Interface (MPI), and the Open Multi-Processing (OpenMP) application programming interface (API). The METIS partitioner [24] is used to decompose the mesh to numerous partitions. The total number of partitions is equal to the number of MPI processes. The code also employs several functions from the Intel Math Kernel Library such as matrix multiplications and matrix-vector multiplications from BLAS (DGEMM, DGEMV) etc.

Previous work done under the PRACE project HOVE [17] revealed that the present code is both CPU and memory bounded, due to the nature of the schemes and implementation employed. Extensive testing in 5 different HPC facilities it was concluded that the major performance bottlenecks were associated with the WENO weights computation (32-59%), the least squares reconstruction (13-36%), and lastly, with the extrapolation of the reconstructed solutions at the Gaussian quadrature points (7-14%). Optimisation of the relevant subroutines by formula rewriting, reduction of operations. Also, the inclusion of linear system libraries significant speed-ups, ranging from 1.5 to 8.5, have been achieved. Especially, the high-order WENO schemes contributed the most. The reader is referred to [5] for more details regarding the implementation.

The UCNS3D code uses the Tecplot libraries for writing Tecplot binary files or Paraview output files of the solutions. The grids in 2D or 3D can be generated with any grid generation software package (such as ICEM-CFD, Pointwise, Gridgen, Gambit), that can export the grid and the boundary conditions in the ANSYS fluent format (ASCII *.msh extension). The UCNS3D code then translates this format to a native format with a separate grid connectivity, coordinates and boundary file in either ASCII or binary format.

2. Software and Hardware Used for Optimisation

The optimisation of the HOVE2 code was performed on the Hazel Hen (Cray XC40) [1]. The Hazel Hen system at HLRS is consisting out of 7712 compute nodes. Each node is a 2-socket system equipped with Intel Haswell (Intel Xeon E5-2680v3) processors and 128 GB of DDR4 main memory. The nodes are connected with the Cray Aries network built on a dragonfly topology. Tests were performed during normal operation of the system.

The performance analysis was performed by using the CrayPAT/X [19] and Score-P [20] tools. The CrayPat/X version 7.0.6 was used for the I/O analysis. The software environment at the moment of the study was CLE with PrgEnv-intel/6.0.5 with the Intel module version 19.0.1.144 [21]. The specification of the measurement setup for CrayPAT/X tool is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Specification of the measurement setup for CrayPAT/X tool.

	Measurement Setup
Nodes	70
Total number of MPI processes	140
OpenMP threads per MPI process	12
Total number of iterations	2
Mesh	Ultrafine: 29907000 hexahedral elements, 195667500 prismatic elements
PAPI counters	None

For the retrieval of the trace and profile information in this paper the Score-P version 3.1 was used. The profile has been analysed by using the Cube tool (version 4.4.3) [22] and the trace was visualized with the Vampir tool (version 9.4.0) [23]. The software environment at the moment of the study was CLE with PrgEnv-intel/6.0.5 with the Intel module version 18.0.1.163. Two runs of the HOVE2 application with different measurement setups were performed: a first one to study the general application structure prior to optimisation and a second one to check the behaviour of the application after optimisation. Both measurement setups for the Score-P tool is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Specification of the measurement setups for Score-P tool.

	Measurement Setup 1	Measurement Setup 2
Nodes	2	10
Total number of MPI processes	4	20
OpenMP threads per MPI process	12	12
Total number of iterations	100	2
Mesh	Medium (STAR.*): 248903 hexahedral elements, 903388 tetrahedral elements, 42915 pyramidal elements, 9248 prismatic elements	Medium (GRID.*): 13644606 tetrahedral elements, 60728 pyramidal elements
PAPI counters	PAPI_TOT_INS PAPI_L2_TCM PAPI_TOT_CYC	PAPI_TOT_INS PAPI_L2_TCM PAPI_TOT_CYC

3. Main Performance Bottlenecks

As mentioned above, the HOVE2 code has been already analysed and optimized. In particular, the UCNS3D CFD solver has been improved. A timeline view of the whole run with the first measurement setup obtained with Score-P and visualized with Vampir is shown in Figure 1. The focus of our current work is the optimisation of the HOVE2 code before and after solver, referred to as Part A and Part C respectively.

Figure 1. Vampir timeline view of HOVE2 running with 4 MPI processes and 12 OpenMP threads per MPI process on 2 nodes of Hazel Hen. Time runs left to right. The timelines of the MPI processes and OpenMP threads are stacked in the vertical direction. Blue colour shows OpenMP synchronization, red colour represents MPI communication, green colour is application code for input/output operations, dark blue colour is solver code.

At the beginning, the application performs the initialization and reads a mesh and the mesh partition from an input file. In the end of the computation, the HOVE2 application writes the data in the several output files, among other things, to a checkpoint file. Accordingly, there are three main performance issues which are given below.

1. The HOVE2 application uses the METIS software package for graph partitioning [24]. METIS provides the best way to minimize inter-domain (inter-CPU) communications. However, this partitioner has limitations: it cannot partition meshes larger than 27 million cells on a 128 GB node. The partitioning is done while the code is running and not in a pre-processing step, and therefore ParMETIS [25] needs to use partition meshes larger than that. ParMETIS is a parallel version of METIS. The integration of ParMETIS with the HOVE2 application has difficulties, associated with conjugation of programming languages. The ParMETIS is written in C++ and it is C++ friendly. The HOVE2 application is written in Fortran 2003.

2. The mesh files have the ASCII format. At start up, each MPI process reads its own part of the mesh based on the partitioning. The implementation of the reading in an original code did not use MPI-IO [26]. Only a master process performed the writing the data to the checkpoint file, after collecting data from the slave processes. Here, the main task is to change a structure of the checkpoint file and implement MPI-IO.
3. Finally, two large global arrays are used for the stencil selection algorithm. Each one is using 48 bytes per cell that are the same across each CPU. This has a large memory footprint and a limitation when very fine meshes are used, for example, for one billion cells, 48 GB of memory are required for each array per MPI process. A hybrid MPI and OpenMP strategy can temporarily solve this problem, but eventually two routines that use these arrays will be made local by each one of them testing how much data they require to complete the stencil algorithm operation, so that these arrays are not global and that they do not have such a memory footprint. There are two more global arrays of 8 bytes used by each CPU, but which are not considered crucial for being redesigned.

3.1. ParMETIS Support

The HOVE2 application calls the *ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway* subroutine [27] from the ParMETIS package. This subroutine *ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway* takes a mesh as input and computes a partitioning of the mesh elements, minimizing the number of cut edges. Internally, *ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway* uses a mesh-to-graph routine and then calls the same core partitioning routine that is used by both *ParMETIS_V3_PartKway* and *ParMETIS_V3_PartGeomKway*.

The key problem for the integration of ParMETIS version 4 in the HOVE2 application is its incompatibility of the types and interfaces. The ParMETIS is designed for programs that are written in C/C++, but the HOVE2 is a Fortran program. The integration of ParMETIS consists of the following steps. They are shown in a prototype example (Figure 2).

1. The Fortran program uses the standard intrinsic module *iso_c_binding*. It defines named constants, types, and procedures for C interoperability.
2. The Fortran program uses compatible internal types for variables that are related to the *ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway* subroutine. We used the types from Table 3.
3. The interface of the *pdivide_mesh_c* subroutine in the *prototype.f90* file is C-compatible.
4. The *pdivide_mesh_c* subroutine is called from the main program.
5. The *pdivide_mesh.c* file is a wrapper which provide a portable change of Fortran MPI communicator into C MPI communicator by using the *MPI_Comm_f2c* [28].

Figure 2. The prototype example with ParMETIS support.

prototype.f90

```

program main
use, intrinsic :: iso_fortran_env
use iso_c_binding
implicit none
include 'mpif.h'

! ParMETIS vars
! IN:
integer(c_int), allocatable :: elmdist(:)
integer(c_int), allocatable :: eptr(:)
...
real(c_float), allocatable :: tpgwts(:)
real(c_float), allocatable :: ubvec(:)

! OUTPUT:
integer :: edgecut           ! number of cut edges
integer*4, allocatable :: part(:) ! distribution

interface
subroutine pdivide_mesh_c(...) &
  bind(c, name='pdivide_mesh_c')
...
end subroutine pdivide_mesh_c
end interface

! main program
...
call pdivide_mesh_c(...)
...
end program main

```

pdivide_mesh.c

```

#include "pmetis.h"
#include "mpi.h"
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <assert.h>

/*****
* Wrapper of ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway
* used to convert communicator from Fortran
* number to whatever type it is in MPI_Comm
* Jakub Sistek 2011
*****/

void pdivide_mesh_c(...)
{
  MPI_Comm comm;
  comm = MPI_Comm_f2c( *commInt );

  ParMETIS_V3_PartMeshKway(...);

  return;
}

```

Table 3: Type replacement in Fortran.

Fortran 2003	Fortran C-binding
integer	integer(c_int)
real	real(c_float)

3.2. MPI-I/O

The HOVE2 application requires optimisation of the reading a mesh file and the writing a checkpoint file. In both cases we will use the MPI collective communications. Collective I/O calls must be made by all processes participating in a particular I/O sequence. Collective I/O also use the “shared file, all write” strategy and will be optimized dynamically by the Cray MPI library [29]. The Cray I/O stack has two techniques: data sieving and aggregation. Data sieving is used to combine lots of small accesses into a single larger one. It allows to reduce the number of operations. Aggregation refers to the concept of moving data through intermediate nodes.

Reading optimisation. Each mesh consists of 3 files: *.cel, *.vrt, *.bnd. The first file contains the connectivity list (index of cell, followed by vertex indices), the second file the coordinates of each vertex (vertex ID followed by coordinates in X, Y, Z axis), and finally by the boundary file (boundary element id followed by vertex ids and boundary condition code). The file that was taking considerable time to read and write was the checkpoint file (*RESTART.dat*). The structure of this file was first the cell index followed by 5 real numbers on each line (it could be more depending on the problem solved) which represent the conserved variables at each cell.

A part of the CrayPAT/X report with the statistics for reading is shown in Table 4. Each MPI process out of 140 reads all files of the STAR mesh. But each MPI process reads only own parts of the mesh based on the partitioning. Most of the time falls on STAR.cel. An average read time per reader process is 161.71 seconds.

Table 4: Reading statistics from the CrayPAT/X report.

Avg Read Time per Reader Rank	Avg Read MiBytes per Reader Rank	Read Rate MiBytes/sec	Number of Reader Ranks	Avg Reads per Reader Rank	Bytes/ Call	File Name=!x/^(proc sys)/PE=HIDE
161.711647	47,462.634741	293.501648	140	6,081,165.3	8,183.99	STAR.cel
36.259266	4,495.825938	123.991091	140	576,875.3	8,171.98	STAR.vrt
3.142078	13,767.975021	4,381.805591	1	3,524,602.0	4,096.00	./tp1Tbpul
3.110464	13,767.975021	4,426.340715	1	3,524,602.0	4,096.00	./tp1GziJnV
2.182215	9,818.326107	4,499.248320	1	2,513,492.0	4,096.00	./tp1Gj8oAY
0.777565	73.103563	94.015970	140	9,361.2	8,188.51	STAR.bnd
0.019677	0.008965	0.455631	140	3.0	3,133.67	UCNS3D.DAT
0.013436	49.165413	3,659.247055	1	12,587.0	4,095.79	./tp1YJTCHU
0.010000	35.003231	3,500.423217	1	8,961.0	4,095.92	./tp1yPn2Gp
0.000058	0.000394	6.791923	140	51.6	8.00	_UnknownFile_

When the HOVE2 application is restarted, the MPI processes read the mesh not from the *STAR.** files, but from the *RESTART.dat* file. Nevertheless, the reading is performed in the same way: each MPI process reads only its part of the mesh. Based on this, the *MPI_TYPE_CREATE_INDEXED_BLOCK* has been to describe the displacements of mesh cells that belongs to each MPI processes [30]. This subroutine creates an indexed datatype with constant-sized blocks. In our case a block has size 5. After creating the datatype (Table 5, line 1-2) the *RESTART.dat* file is opened only for reading (line 3). The *MPI_FILE_SET_VIEW* subroutine changes the process's view of the data in the *RESTART.dat* file (line 4-5). The *MPI_FILE_READ_ALL* performs collective reading using an individual file pointer (line 6-7). The *MPI_FILE_CLOSE* call closes the *RESTART.dat* file (line 8) and the *MPI_TYPE_FREE* call frees the datatype with indexed blocks (line 9).

Table 5: File Source code for parallel reading data from a checkpoint file.

```

1 call MPI_TYPE_CREATE_INDEXED_BLOCK(KMAXE,n_end,DISPT,MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION,DATATYPE,IERROR)
2 call MPI_TYPE_COMMIT(DATATYPE,IERROR)
3 call MPI_FILE_OPEN(MPI_COMM_WORLD,'RESTART.dat',MPI_MODE_RDONLY,MPI_INFO_NULL, fh, IERROR)
4 call MPI_FILE_SET_VIEW(fh, disp_in_file, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, DATATYPE,
5 'native', MPI_INFO_NULL, IERROR)
6 call MPI_FILE_READ_ALL(fh, ARRAY, KMAXE*n_end, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION,
7 MPI_STATUS_IGNORE, IERROR)
8 call MPI_FILE_CLOSE(fh, IERROR)
9 call MPI_TYPE_FREE(DATATYPE,IERROR)

```

Writing optimisation. The CrayPAT/X statistics for writing are presented in Table 6. Only the master process writes the checkpoint file (*RESTART.dat*), does the plots, writes a log file (*history.txt*) as well as a file with statistics and other data. Prior to this, each slave process sends own parts of the mesh to the master process. The master process spends 1.15 hours on reading the checkpoint file.

Table 6: Writing statistics from the CrayPAT/X report.

Avg Write Time per Writer Rank	Avg Write MiBytes per Writer Rank	Write Rate MiBytes/sec	Number of Writer Ranks	Avg Writes per Writer Rank	Bytes/Call	File Name=!x/^/(proc sys)/PE=HIDE
4,155.568795	10,325.981159	2.484854	1	225,574,501.0	48.00	RESTART.dat
98.164910	9,818.326153	100.018695	1	2,189,205,649.0	4.70	./tp1Gj8oAY
90.504975	13,767.975143	152.123960	1	1,804,596,044.0	8.00	./tp1Tbpuu1
90.400594	13,767.975143	152.299610	1	1,804,596,044.0	8.00	./tp1GziJnV
27.012153	13,767.975338	509.695599	1	3,524,683.0	4,095.91	OUT_2.plt
25.736539	13,767.975338	534.958315	1	3,524,683.0	4,095.91	OUT_0.plt
18.228055	9,818.326294	538.638188	1	2,513,539.0	4,095.92	GRID.plt
0.325327	49.165504	151.126426	1	6,444,226.0	8.00	./tp1YJTCHU
0.306869	35.003277	114.065757	1	6,736,017.0	5.45	./tp1yPn2Gp
0.098529	49.165676	498.994865	1	12,654.0	4,074.12	SURF_2.plt
0.066250	35.003418	528.350895	1	9,008.0	4,074.57	SURF.plt
0.037728	0.002287	0.060615	1	56.0	42.82	history.txt
0.019981	0.000136	0.006825	1	5.0	28.60	fort.100
0.011093	0.000351	0.031639	1	3.0	122.67	STATISTICS.txt
0.000753	0.000076	0.101361	1	1.0	80.00	Errors.dat

In order to implement MPI-IO for writing a checkpoint file, we changed its structure. Now, this file needs to be written in a specific order following the index number of the cells, such that each line contains only 5 or more real numbers representing the conserved variables within each cell.

Similarly, the *MPI_TYPE_CREATE_INDEXED_BLOCK* was used for creating a datatype (Table 7). In this case, we open the *restart.dat* file for writing or create the file if it does not exist (line 3-4). The *MPI_FILE_SET_VIEW* subroutine changes the process's view of the data in the *restart.dat* file (line 5-6). The *MPI_FILE_WRITE_ALL* performs collective writing (line 7-8). The *MPI_FILE_CLOSE* call closes the *restart.dat* file (line 9) and the *MPI_TYPE_FREE* call frees the datatype with indexed blocks (line 10).

Table 7: File Source code for parallel writing data to a checkpoint file.

```

1 call MPI_TYPE_CREATE_INDEXED_BLOCK(KMAXE,n_end,DISPT,MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION,DATATYPE,IERROR)
2 call MPI_TYPE_COMMIT(DATATYPE,IERROR)
3 call MPI_FILE_OPEN(MPI_COMM_WORLD,'RESTART.dat',MPI_MODE_WRONLY + MPI_MODE_CREATE,
4 MPI_INFO_NULL,fh,IERROR)
5 call MPI_FILE_SET_VIEW(fh,disp_in_file,MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION,DATATYPE,
6 'native',MPI_INFO_NULL,IERROR)
7 call MPI_FILE_WRITE_ALL(fh,ARRAY,KMAXE*n_end,MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION,
8 MPI_STATUS_IGNORE,IERROR)
9 call MPI_FILE_CLOSE(fh,IERROR)
10 call MPI_TYPE_FREE(DATATYPE,IERROR)

```

3.3. Redesign of the Global Arrays

After implementing the ParMETIS support and the I/O optimisation, the runtime for part A and part C has become acceptable (Figure 1). The two global arrays concerned with the stencil algorithm have been modified and are now made local to each CPU, resulting in a significantly reduced memory footprint. The role of the first global array was to store the direct side neighbours of all elements in the grid. The role of the second array was to store all the elements that share each vertex for all the vertices in the grid. These two arrays were then used by the stencil selection algorithms to build the stencil region around each considered element/vertex until the required number of elements has been reached. Obviously when the size of the mesh was increased significantly these two arrays would not fit in the memory. Therefore, both of them had been made local, by the following strategy:

- Each processor (MPI process) stores an array of the connectivity (neighbour of every element, elements belonging to every vertex) for its own cells and the processors that it shares a boundary with.
- If the stencil algorithm still does not find the required neighbours in his proximity, then the connectivity array is populated with the connectivity list from the neighbours taken from neighbour processes, until the stencil selection algorithm for all the cells within the processor is completed.
- For all the tests performed, there were no more than two layers or processors connectivity lists required for completing the stencil algorithms.

4. Results

After I/O optimisation, an experiment without instrumentation tools was conducted. The HOVE2 application on a mesh of 320 million cells on 70 compute nodes with 140 MPI processes was launched. The total runtime taken to initialise the code, to perform two iterations and finally write the output and the checkpoint file for an ILES simulation of WENO 5th-order scheme improved from 18 hours to 14 minutes (Table 8). The acceleration is 77 times. The implementation of collective writing reduced the write time from 6 hours to 2 minutes. The speedup is 180.

Table 8: Runtimes before and after optimisation on 70 compute nodes.

	Before optimisation	After optimisation	Speedup
Total runtime	18 hours	14 min	77.14
Write time of the checkpoint file	6 hours	2 min	180

5. Further Optimisation

In the end of this project, an experiment with 20 MPI processes on 10 compute nodes was performed. A timeline view of the whole run with the second measurement setup (Table 2) obtained with Score-P and visualized with Vampir is shown in Figure 3. Here, there are 3 regions for further optimisation.

Region I is shown in Figure 4. There is a load imbalance in the *renumber_neighbours_* subroutine. For example, MPI rank 18 processes a larger chunk of data than the rest. But this is not of concern, since the subroutine is renumbering the neighbours within each process based on which processors the neighbours belong to. This happens only during the initialisation of the code, which is negligible (approximately 30 seconds), compared to the total run time.

Region II contains the *outwritegridb_* subroutine (Figure 5). This one has a serial implementation: only the master process writes the grid in the Tecplot or Paraview format. Currently, the similar MPI-IO indexed block will be implemented on the Paraview output format and further optimisation work involves the utilisation of the parallel Tecplot I/O library for the Tecplot output.

There is a load imbalance in the *outwrite3vb_* subroutine in Region III (Figure 6). Almost all the work in this case is performed by the master process. The *outwrite3vb_* subroutine serves to write the solution file in Tecplot or Paraview format. Currently, the similar MPI-IO indexed block will be also implemented on the Paraview output format and further optimisation work is required to use the parallel Tecplot I/O library for the Tecplot output.

Figure 3. Vampir timeline view of HOVE2 running with 20 MPI processes and 12 OpenMP threads per MPI process on 10 nodes of Hazel Hen. Time runs left to right. The timelines of the MPI processes and OpenMP threads are stacked in the vertical direction. Orange colour shows OpenMP loops, red colour represents MPI communication, green colour is application code. The blue frames show the regions for further research.

Figure 4. Region I: load imbalance in the *renumber_neighbours_* subroutine.

I

Figure 5. Region II: serial implementation of the *outwritegridb_* subroutine.

II

Figure 6. Region III: load imbalance in the *outwrite3vb_* subroutine.

III

Summary and Conclusion

This work on the HOVE2 code is a continuation of a previous one, during which the UCNS3D CFD solver has been improved. The current paper focused on the ParMETIS support and the MPI-IO implementation. The ParMETIS package is needed for working with big meshes. It was shown that parallel I/O reduces the runtime, allowing to properly use hardware resources (for example, a Lustre storage) and the existing MPI-IO library in an efficient way (like Cray MPI-IO library).

The following modifications have been made in the original HOVE2 source code:

1. Optional ParMETIS support was added. The issue with the incompatibility of the types and interfaces has been solved.
2. Collective MPI communications were added for reading and writing the checkpoint file.
3. Elimination of two global arrays associated with the stencil algorithm, and replacement by two local arrays.

After optimisation, the complete time taken to initialise the code, performing two iterations and writing the output and checkpoint files for an ILES simulation of WENO 5th-order scheme on a mesh of 320 million cells on 70 nodes, improved from 18 hours to 14 minutes. The write time of the checkpoint file on 70 nodes was improved from approximately 6 hours to 2 minutes.

Further optimisation is planned, which implement the parallel Tecplot I/O subroutines, since the extension of indexed block MPI-IO similar to RESTART.dat to Paraview solution format is straight forward and well under development.

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Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE projects funded in part by the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 730913 and 823767.